

EDUCATION OF CHILDREN - THE IMPORTANCE OF COMMUNICATIVE APPROACH IN THE EDUCATION PROCESS

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Abstract. *In this article, opinions are expressed about the importance of communicative approach in the process of education and upbringing of children in preschool educational organizations and the development of communicative competencies of educators. Information on the professional activity and psychological position of the teacher in the development of communicative competence is given.*

Keywords: *reflection, physiology, pedagogical educator, mental ability, communicative competence, ICT competence, emotional competence, innovative activity.*

INTRODUCTION

Analyzing the wide-scale creativity and innovation being carried out in New Uzbekistan, which is on the threshold of the Third Renaissance under the motto "From national revival to national rise", in particular, the reforms carried out in the education system, the words of the head of our state that "New Uzbekistan begins at the threshold of the school" are not only a school we understand that education has set a number of tasks for the preschool education system. Communicative competence has a social character, and for its formation in children, it is necessary to organize a process based on general didactic, specific principles and innovative approaches. Communicative competences are specified as a separate criterion in the framework of competences in the field of development of children of preschool age in the state requirements. All over the world, at the same time, in our republic, the issue of intensive preparation of preschool children for school education through comprehensive development in the preschool education system is considered urgent. Priority is given to improving the methodology of speech activity and vocabulary development of pupils, developing a methodical system of forming communicative competence in preschool children, developing communicative skills of pupils based on modern technologies. In particular, in the concept of the development of the preschool education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030, priority tasks such as "creating conditions for the intellectual, moral, aesthetic and physical development of preschool children in all aspects, introducing innovations, advanced pedagogical and information and communication technologies into the preschool education system defined.

Currently, the main task of the educational process is to produce a competitive specialist for the society. According to the results of the research, most employers prefer to sign a contract with an employee who has the skills of independent study, quick and effective decision-making when necessary, and constant analysis (reflection) of his work. they see a slave. Therefore, first of all, an educator must be educated, know the great life he lives, understand the laws of nature and society, be socially active, master the pedagogy of general and preschool education, the psychology and physiology of children, and know the characteristics of young children. Also, the pedagogic educator's approach to the analysis of events from a scientific point of view makes it

possible to realize the success of the comprehensive development of the child. For this purpose, the tasks of equipping the growing young generation with knowledge, our national values, restoring our spirituality, introducing them to world culture, masterpieces of our national culture, and educating them to be physically healthy and spiritually mature have been set. For this, the ability of each educator to demand and control himself is a guarantee of the fulfillment of the requirements set by our state for preschool education organizations. This includes:

- Maintaining and strengthening the child's health.
- Increase mental ability.
- Formation of beliefs and views that correspond to the ideological and mental principles of our national value and spirituality.
- Formation of love for motherland, social activity. To inculcate the sense of friendship, honesty and hard work in the young generation
- Communicative competence is a holistic quality that synthesizes general culture and its specific manifestations in professional activity.

Today, the importance of communicative competence as an important feature of a teacher of a preschool educational organization is announced at the normative, scientific, theoretical and methodological level. At the same time, the analysis of pedagogical activity shows that not all teachers meet the necessary level of development of communicative competence. It sets the task of creating a complex system of measures to improve the psychological training and retraining of pedagogues of preschool educational institutions in this direction.

The formation of the professional competence of the teacher of preschool educational organizations is a combination of professional and general human relations, as a result of which it is possible not only to effectively manage the educational process, but also to successfully solve the difficulties that arise during the performance of tasks. This undoubtedly affects the improvement of professional pedagogical competence and the development of pedagogical skills. At this stage of educational development, the competency-based approach is the leading direction in the activities of preschool educators. The professional competence of teachers of this preschool educational organization is the acquisition of experience, knowledge skills, techniques and methods necessary for the accurate performance of the professional tasks of educators of the preschool educational organization. The professional competence of a preschool educator is a set of competencies: methodological, psychological and pedagogical, communicative, research, presentation, ICT competence, emotional competence. In order to improve and develop professional competences, the educator of a young preschool educational organization should go through the following stages:

- Development of professional competences of pre-school education teacher
- Work in stylistic associations, creative groups, research activities
- Development of innovative activities, new pedagogical technologies
- Active participation in pedagogical competitions, scientific-practical conferences
- Promotion of best practice

The work of a teacher in a preschool educational organization is described as an activity characterized by intuition, inspiration, ingenuity and ingenuity. The creative activity of a teacher is not carried out according to a template, because its integral components are originality, rejection of clichés, surprise, the ability to act intuitively depending on the situation. Currently, not only educators, but also pedagogues-researchers, pedagogues - psychologists, pedagogues - technologists are in demand, therefore one of the main components of the professional competence

of a preschool teacher is his ability to manage himself. Self-education is a system of intellectual and ideological self-education, which implies voluntary and moral self-improvement, but does not set them as its goal. Creativity, motivation, purposefulness and other personal qualities of a pedagogue play an important role in self-education.

Self-education of a teacher is a necessary condition for his professional activity. Society has always set the highest demands on pedagogues and teachers. You need to know more than anyone to teach others. Self-education is a purposeful cognitive activity controlled by the individual; acquisition of systematic knowledge in any field of science, technology, culture, etc. The process of self-education is the following activity:

- is carried out voluntarily;
- is carried out consciously;
- planned, managed and controlled by the person himself.

The activity of the teacher in the field of self-education should include the following: study and introduction of new pedagogical technologies, forms, methods and methods of teaching; participation in the lessons of colleagues, participation in the exchange of pedagogical experience; in self-analysis of one's professional activity; increase knowledge in classical and modern psychology and pedagogy; in studying the events of modern economic, political and cultural life; in increasing their level of knowledge, legal and general culture.

The set of skills that make up the teacher's communicative competence includes the skills of analyzing and evaluating the communicative situation, setting goals, choosing and using the means of implementing a plan and correcting it, and evaluating the effectiveness of the result. to produce a full-fledged communicative act; the ability to choose communication strategies adequate to the situation, the ability to establish communication taking into account the gender and age, socio-cultural, status characteristics of people, the ability to actively respond to changes in the situation, reconstruction taking into account the communication. changes in the partner's emotional mood, conducting a conversation, discussing, reaching agreements, using words to conduct communication psychotherapy, analyzing communication conflicts.

An adequate level of communicative competence for the effective professional activity of a teacher consists of the following abilities: to provide a socio-psychological forecast of the communicative situation for communication; programming the communication process based on the uniqueness of the communicative situation; implementation of socio-psychological management of communication processes; establishing communication at different psychological distances; flexibility and adequacy in changing psychological positions. E.A. Klimov identified the main features of the teacher's communicative competence:

- ability to lead, teach, educate; the ability to listen and listen;
- broad outlook;
- speech (communicative) culture;
- the spiritual orientation of consciousness, the ability or ability to observe the manifestations of a person's feelings, consciousness and character, his behavior, mental representation of his inner world, modeling, not attaching himself or others to it ;
 - a design approach to a person based on the belief that a person can always be better;
 - empathy;
 - monitoring;
 - ability to solve non-standard situations;
 - high level of self-regulation.

The teacher's professional communication skills and abilities include:
the ability to actively listen, form opinions, describe behavior, attract people; the ability to keep the client at a distance and avoid emotional closeness;
empathy as a skill;
the ability to use strategies that contribute to changes in the client's behavior, the ability to focus on given objects and events, the ability to reflect them objectively and adequately.

Important communicative qualities of a teacher include: the tendency to communicate with people, politeness, the ability to effectively resolve conflicts, fluency in verbal and non-verbal means of communication, comfort, logical and clear speech, politeness, sense of humor and others.

CONCLUSION

In short, communicative competence is the main component of a teacher's professional competence. It includes the following: a high level of speech development, which allows a person to freely perceive and transmit information in the process of communication; active listening skills, feedback formation; understanding the language of non-verbal communication; the ability to correctly assess the interlocutor as a person and choose one's communication strategy based on this assessment; it is the ability to respond adequately to the situation and use its specific features to achieve one's communicative goals, to positively feel one's personality in the interlocutor.

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